

**MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR ASSESSING THE CRIMINOGENIC STATE OF
AN ADMINISTRATIVE TERRITORY IN THE ACTIVITIES OF A
PREVENTION INSPECTOR**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13981057>

Based on the instructions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, on ensuring employment and improving the standard of living of the population, a completely new system has been introduced. This system includes large-scale measures to identify and address the problems of families and citizens in need of social protection, including the "Iron Notebook," "Women's Notebook," and "Youth Notebook" at the sectoral level. Building on this system, "Mahallabay," "Oilabay," and "Fuqarobay" approaches are currently being implemented in our republic, serving to improve the interaction of internal affairs bodies, particularly prevention inspectors, with mahallas and citizens. Information and analytical activities have always been carried out in every society and in various spheres of public life.

A thorough analysis of our country's development path and the growing need to ensure the security of individuals, society, and the state have necessitated the introduction of fundamentally new approaches and mechanisms to further improve the system of state bodies, particularly internal affairs bodies. This highlights the need for comprehensive study of current societal issues and the development of advanced methods for continuous analysis of existing legislation, law enforcement practices, and leading international experiences.

At an extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dedicated to a comprehensive analysis of the country's socio-economic development results in 2016 and defining the most important directions and priorities of the government's economic and social program for 2017, President Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized to the conference participants: "It is necessary to focus on a thorough analysis of existing shortcomings and their root causes, rather than merely reporting on work completed." The increasing threats to global development and security, primarily the growing influence of transnational crimes and foreign ideologies, require the establishment of a modern and effective system for their elimination and timely prevention.

There is a growing need to continue well-thought-out and consistent actions to make crime prevention the main focus in the fight against crime, and to further improve the organizational and legal mechanisms for preventing and eliminating law violations.

The activities of ensuring public order and security in some states and administrative territories are provided in various ways and methods. Each state has its own advanced experience in this area, and their study and implementation in the system of ensuring public order and security of our country is one of the urgent requirements of today. According to D.V. Vasiliev, studying foreign experience in combating crime allows for the identification of important directions and pathways for societal development, preventing errors and misconceptions in the process of humanity's long-term historical development.

The system of combating crime in each state differs from that of other countries in certain, unique aspects. The study of the experience of the United States of America in analyzing the characteristics of crime and the laws of developed countries aimed at its prevention is of great importance, as it is a country with a unique system and advanced experience. The experience of developed countries in the field under study (including the USA, Canada, Great Britain, Germany, India, and Australia) shows that the effectiveness of crime prevention is directly linked to the implementation of special programs and projects implemented in them.

The system's developer is Accenture, which focuses on preventing crimes committed by organized crime groups. This system is deployed in all 32 districts of London and automatically performs statistical analysis based on information collected by the police and can predict the place, time and other characteristics of possible crimes. Accenture has previously developed software similar to Precrime for the Spanish and Singaporean police, and this algorithm is constantly being improved, and its electronic intelligence forecasts are becoming increasingly accurate.

According to the latest data, this program has been tested, but due to its high cost, it is not possible to implement it in all cities. Since late 2014, the Berlin police have been testing the "Precobs" program, created by German engineers, to predict the commission of crimes today with high accuracy. The screening system has elevated the technologies used in crime prevention to a new level. This system is presented by researchers from the Department of Artificial Intelligence Research at the Polytechnic University of Madrid.

The system can predict future aggressive actions based on people's facial expressions and emotions through video surveillance. In the United States, this system has also been implemented, and its main goal is to identify dangerous intentions of passengers. This system is primarily used to prevent terrorist acts. The first stage of testing with this system was completed in 2011.

The program also faced criticism from researchers. Some scientists wonder if they can distinguish between the specificity of the program and the habitual anxiety reflected on the face, the intention of causing harm from the behavior. Because it is said that when scanning or examining fingerprints, many legal travelers may have a nervous breakdown and their heart rate may be increased. However, this program justifies itself by its accuracy and lack of error. That is, the accuracy of the screening system's laboratory test indicators exceeds 70%. Individuals with such an antisocial orientation are characterized by a small age group and a high level of skill in effectively choosing favorable for them criminogenic situations as a result of increased physical strength or predisposition to crime.

According to A.N. Pastushen, "criminogenic propensity of a person is a personal propensity (permissible) to commit a specific type of crime under certain conditions and serves as an opportunity for a person's "potential" criminal behavior." (Potential - lot. Potentia - potential - is a resource used to solve a task and achieve the intended goal) 4. In our view, any criminogenic situation on its own does not lead to the commission of an offense by a person. After all, offenses are committed not due to sudden criminogenic situations, but as a result of the formation of certain stable personal negative qualities of a person and a contempt for values and laws. Therefore, the biophysiological nature of a person is a necessary condition for their individuality, indicating their uniqueness and uniqueness.

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